

Conflict over the Conflict: The Restriction of Palestine Solidarity and Academic Freedom in Germany

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Universities in Germany have historically been sites where broader political struggles are shaped. These institutions are not just places of learning; they are arenas where societal tensions are debated and challenged. It is therefore not surprising that global solidarity protests for Gaza have also emerged on campuses globally. Within the context of Germany, these protests diffused into the local repertoire towards the end of November 2023. Minor vigils and rallies had taken place at higher education institutions and arts colleges. However, it was not until the occupation of a lecture hall of Freie Universität Berlin that protesters in solidarity with the besieged population of Gaza realized the full potential of universities as key arenas of contention. As the student protests moved into focus, they initiated a new media cycle centered on the transnational diffusion of the war in Israel/Palestine onto German campuses which reached its peak with the establishment of several protest camps in May 2024

(Figure 1). At the same time, controversies sparked by attempts to police and contain the campus protests that fundamentally linked the mobilization efforts in solidarity with Palestinians to the topic of academic freedom, thus opening up an additional and entirely new arena of contestation.

Student protests on German university campuses were not only driven by the suffering in Gaza but have also responded to the lack of vocal academic engagement. The reluctance of professors and academic leaders to speak out about the humanitarian and political dimensions of a war that leading experts in the field have characterized as genocidal (Bartov 2024; Segal and Daniele 2024; Goldman 2024) has amplified student frustration, contributing to a growing sense of alienation and mistrust between students and faculty. The reasons for this alienation are not endemic to universities. The broader public discourse surrounding the Gaza war has become in-

Figure 1. Reported protest events in solidarity with Palestine in Berlin, 7 October 2023 - 15 September 2024, authors' original event catalogue, coding source: Rundfunk Berlin Brandenburg (RBB, <https://www.rbb24.de/>).

creasingly polarized, with criticism of Israel frequently equated with antisemitism. This conflation has created a tense atmosphere on campuses, where expressing solidarity with Palestinians or critiquing Israeli government actions risks being labeled as antisemitic (see Younes and Al-Taher 2024). Fear of professional or personal repercussions from such labels has discouraged many academics from engaging in open discussions about the conflict. This lack of “academic integrity” (Grimm 2024), in turn, fueled student unrest, as many feel that the intellectual community, traditionally seen as a space for critical debate and emancipatory ideas, was failing to fulfill its role at a critical moment.

The higher education institutions in Berlin, and especially Freie Universität Berlin (FUB) became the epicenter of contentious politics. FUB has traditionally played a pivotal role in student protest. Established in 1948 as a response to political oppression in the Soviet-controlled universities of Berlin's Eastern sector, FUB cultivated a tradition of critical thought and social engagement. In 1966, one of its lecture halls also became the site of Ger-

many's first student sit-in. This occupation marked a turning point in German student activism and set the stage for the 1968 protests for democratic reforms and against the Vietnam War. When “Students for Palestine” occupied a lecture hall at FUB in November 2023, they tapped into this legacy of contentious campus activity and anti-war activism. By demanding a ceasefire in Gaza, an engagement with Israel's human rights violations within the context of the university, and the rejection of the IHRA-definition of antisemitism, they also followed their historical model of linking domestic and external grievances through protest. Likewise, university management initially kept with the tradition of tolerating peaceful protest, which included panel talks, workshops, and live music. However, political pressure and animosities between protesters and counter-protesters soon led the presidency to reverse course and to order the eviction of the protesters.

The decision to call the police on campus became a trigger event for an entire episode of contention. On the one hand, footage of police forces inside the university buildings

went viral sparking global criticism and catalyzing the formation of the “Student Coalition Berlin” as an organizing mechanism between activists from Berlin’s different campuses. On the other hand, it also laid path dependencies for the ways how the administrations were to deal with student protests. Amid its decision to evict, the FUB management also filed criminal charges for trespassing against the student protesters, thus creating new grievances for subsequent student mobilizations. In addition, the Berlin Senate moved to reinstate disciplinary regulations at Berlin universities, supported by presidencies of FUB, Humboldt University Berlin (HUB), and Universität der Künste (UdK). These punitive measures included the forced exmatriculation of students which had been abolished in 2021 due to questions over its constitutionality.

The backlash to these repressive developments materialized most visibly in the shape of heightened contentious activity on campus in the summer semester of 2024. On May 7, activists gathered in an open courtyard at FUB and set up tents. No access to a FUB building was required to get to the courtyard and all classrooms remained accessible. Still, within an hour, the university administration ordered the eviction of the camp in coordination with the Berlin Senate, thus rejecting all student attempts to negotiate the terms of their encampment. Upon the request of the FUB management, police forces cleared the area, resorting to excessive force against the peaceful protesters, including batons and pepper spray. Over 70 people were arrested, and over 150 criminal investigations and investigations into administrative offenses were filed (*Der Tagesspiegel Online* 2024). Merely two weeks later, HUB witnessed similar

events on May 25, 2024. Students who had occupied the social science faculty building and renamed it the “Jabalia Institute” were forcibly removed from campus by police units in spite of prior agreement with the university management that the protests would be temporarily tolerated. In a press statement, HUB president Julia von Blumenthal indicated that the eviction had been directly ordered by the Mayor of Berlin (Würzer 2024).

The repression of protest on campus paired with the unprecedented intervention by state politicians into higher education autonomy became a critical juncture for the protest cycle, opening up the topic of academic freedom as a new additional field of contestation. This became most visible when almost 400 lecturers from Berlin universities publicly opposed how the protests had been handled by university management.¹ Their statement in defense of students’ right to protest sparked a massive backlash in the shape of an unprecedented defamation campaign to frame the campus protests as antisemitic and those defending them as supportive of violence and hatred against Jews. In a direct reference to the terminology commonly used to refer to the National Socialists and their responsibility for the Shoah, the German tabloid “Bild-Zeitung” went on to brand those who had co-signed the letter as “perpetrators” (UniversiTäter) on 10 May 2023, paired with portraits that were reminiscent of the infamous mugshots of the “Academics for Peace” published by Turkish media in 2016 (Baser, Akgönül, and Öztürk 2017). This analogy was only reinforced by the German Minister of Education and Research who publicly questioned the loyalty of signatories to the German constitution, effectively placing them in a relation of equivalence with extremists and

¹ https://docs.google.com/forms/d/e/1FAIpQLSfVy2D5Xy_DMiaMx2TsE7YediR6qifxoLDP1zIjKzEl9t1LWw/viewform.

alleged supporters of Hamas. These accusations triggered a wave of threats and hate mail against the signatories of the letter and demonstrated the extent to which politicians were willing to go in their efforts to control the narrative surrounding secondary events linked to Gaza. Amid prominent calls to place “extremists” at German universities under government surveillance (Kain et al. 2024), in mid-June, investigative journalists exposed how leading officials within the Federal Ministry of Education and Research had explored the option to retract public funding from the signatories of the letter and to press charges against them for incitement of hatred (Monroy 2024).

Implications

Investigating Germany as a national context in which responses to October 7 have been particularly polarized offers additional insights into the ways transregional patterns of solidarity are concurrently shaped by the primary conflict in Israel and Palestine and more localized discursive and political dynamics, contentious legacies and community relations. The sketched-out developments offer insights into the parameters within which universities can function as arenas for negotiating social values in the context of international conflicts. As politicized spaces, universities have often proven strategically important sites for activism due to their visibility, accessibility, and high concentration of social and cultural capital. Protesters in solidarity with Gaza are now resorting to the very same tactics that others successfully adopted before them. Most recently, the climate movement was able to generate huge positive resonance through collective action on campus, including classroom occupations and protest camps. In fact, the climate coalition “End Fossil: Occupy!” had occupied a lecture

room at Humboldt University Berlin merely a year before the Palestine protests. Yet, the response of authorities to these protests differed significantly, highlighting the function of universities as micro-arenas within larger arenas of conflict (Jasper 2015). Within the context of a “moral panic” (Della Porta 2024) that has taken hold of German society in the aftermath of October 7th, universities overwhelmingly addressed the protests in solidarity with Palestine through carceral logics. As student protesters and those defending them were publicly vilified, university administrations fed into these securitizing narratives by depicting their activities as disruptive, irresponsible, or even violent. This portrayal effectively shifted public attention away from the protesters’ messages – namely the focus on the violence in Gaza – to debates about the legitimacy of protest and the limits of academic freedom. More significantly, however, these narratives also lay path dependencies by normalizing police intervention, disciplinary actions and restrictions as the go to mechanism in dealing with dissent on campus.

The Berlin case thus offers an illustrative case to study the consequences of securitization of campus politics and state intervention into university autonomy, as well as the implications of external pressures on academic freedom and free speech. As universities are discursively branded as spaces of antisemitism and exclusion, they become elements of a broader culture war in which students and scholars represent potential security threats requiring attention and control. As Younes and Al-Taher note: “Within such ‘tropes,’ the interpellations of Hamas and Antisemitism move effortlessly between racialized student bodies in Berlin and an actual Palestinian armed resistance in the Middle East” (Younes and Al-Taher 2024, 8). At the same time, the escalating secondary conflict (Stern and

Strossen 2020) on campus has also served as a catalyst for resistance and prompted unprecedented organizing efforts within academia, a sector notorious for its individualism and low unionization rate.

Both scholars and institutions have shown signs of pushback against political interference and infringements of academic freedom. Their resistance reflects growing awareness of the need to protect the integrity of higher education against authoritarian trends. A key outcome in this respect has been the formation of solidarity networks between academics and civil society. Bridging different sectors, these alliances provide more sustainable mobilizing structures that are likely to outlast the campus protests. Student activists too have shown remarkable resilience to repression. The ways how universities have handled peaceful protest camps, however, has affected their contentious repertoires. Moderate forms

of activism, such as political rallies, the occupation of lecture halls, or die-ins in university cafeterias, are increasingly replaced by more disruptive direct actions. This shift ultimately illustrates how the policing of nonviolent and moderate forms of contention, in a backfire effect (Lindekilde 2014) can feed confrontation and radical tactics that may prove even harder to address.

Finally, the process by which the controversy over protest in solidarity with Palestine branched out into a broader debate on the limits of academic freedom can serve as a starting point for an in-depth exploration of the intersections between academia, activism, and state power. The case of Germany illustrates how universities are transformed from spaces of free intellectual exchange into political battlegrounds that are forcing institutions to take sides and undermine their traditional role as sites for critical thinking. Ironically,

Figure 2. Promotional ad by the city of Berlin close to the epicentre of mobilization in solidarity with Palestine at Hermannplatz. The ad reads “Four of the best universities in Germany, five if you count the streets.” Picture by Lilian Mauthofer.

Berlin's newest promotional slogan, "Four of the best universities in Germany, five if you count the streets," captures this dynamic (Figure 2). Seeking to highlight Berlin's academic excellence, the slogan inadvertently points to the fact that the streets surrounding universities are often as significant as the institutions themselves in shaping political and social discourse. The very idea that Berlin's "fifth university" is found in the streets underscores the deep connection between intellectual spaces and public activism – a connection that is under critical threat. ♦

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